

The Influence of Religion in Nigerian Politics: Implications for Nation Building

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Abstract

The rate and manner religion influences politics in Nigeria today calls for concern and investigation on its implication for nation building which is the core essence of political social contract. It is indeed a fact that religion and its values are indispensable to human moral development as well as in building functional social institutions such as education, economy, family, and politics of any society. Since Nigerian independence, religious influence in politics has been characterized by certain unhealthy factors among which are differences in religious perception, belief, ideology, faith conceptualization, politics of religious sentiments and undue influence of religion on the secularity of Nigerian state. The work, however, acknowledges the existential relationship between religion and politics, rates religious values indispensable to politics of value, human moral development, ethical leadership, integrity among other virtues needed in nation building. Data were collected from both primary and secondary sources while descriptive research approach and functional theory were used for the interpretation. The researcher identified among other factors, that religion influences political behaviour in Nigeria. It further x-rayed its enormous implications for nation building and its components via national unity, peace, economy, human rights, leadership, education and human development. The research recommended among others, legal restriction of religious extremism on political affairs in Nigeria, deployment of religious virtues of justices, fairness and transparency in politics as well as strict adherence to electoral framework in order to achieve ethical leadership, unbiased electioneering, capacity and competency. This article recommends among others, conscious adherence to the tenets of secularism, respect for human rights, equity and justice inherent in religious values in the practice of politics in Nigeria.

Keywords: *Influence, Religion, secularism, Politics and Nation building*

Introduction

The pervasive influence of religion in Nigerian politics since Independence and the implications for nation building indeed calls for concern and academic investigation. Religion from time immemorial has demonstrated potent force to influence and to permeate virtually all aspects of human life- politically, legally, morally, socially, economically, educationally and culturally. Religion, as well, has proven to be an integrator of culture by which all human experience comes into scrutiny. It is very clear that studies carried out by numerous scholars of diverse academic backgrounds have shown that religion can have positive or negative influence in human society. Positively, religious values and political ideology do complement each other in relationship in enhancing transformative leadership and in building functional social institutions. As such, religion remains vital to human moral and spiritual development, regulating people's way of life, promoting ethical leadership, enhancing the rule of law and as well, acts as a unification therapy for social cohesion and communal harmony. Politics on the other hand deals with governance, security, law and decision making, management and distribution of resources among other key roles that promote good life.

Unfortunately, some elites in their quests for political position have negatively deployed religion as an instrument to gain unmerited advantage. The plethora effects of this on nation building and its processes calls for open- minded probe and urgent redress. Sequel to this, this work is aimed at investigating the underlying problems associated with religion and politics in Nigeria, the factors influencing religious politics in a pluralistic and multicultural state like Nigeria and the implications for nation building. The work further examines the contribution of religious positive values in developing friendly political space for nation building.

Conceptual Clarification

For better understanding of this study, the following key words are worthy of definition: religion, politics and nation building.

Religion

The term religion is derived from the Latin word “*religare*” meaning to bind. It has its root to the Latin noun, *religio* meaning respect for what is sacred, reverence for the gods, sense of right, moral obligation, sanctity and the bond between man and the gods. Harper, cited in Anameje defines religion as an organized collection of belief systems, cultural systems and world-views that relate humanity to spirituality and to moral values.¹ To Merriam Webster, “Religion is the “outward existence of God. To whom obedience, service and honour are due, the feeling or expression of human love, fear or awe of some superhuman and over-ruling power, whether by profession of belief, by observance of rites and ceremonies or by the conduct of life”². In the same vein, Nmah in Umeanolue defines religion from four basic points of views namely: subjectively, objectively, morally and institutionally. Subjectively, religion is man’s natural and innate consciousness of his dependence on a transcendent supra-human Being and the consequent natural and spontaneous propensity to render homage and worship to him. Objectively, religion may be defined as a complex or configuration of doctrines, laws and rituals by which man expresses his loyalty to a transcendental Being, God. Morally, religion as a virtue in a person, an enduring quality, a habit, which disposes him who has it to pay, steadfastly and well, the depth of honour and worship that he owes to God. In the same vein, religion as an institution is defined as possessing its own definite system of beliefs, system of activities and system of values, like any other social institution.³ However, the present study will make use of the definition of religion by Obiefuna who sees religion as a phenomenon in human society. It is part of life, that shapes the traditions of society- marriage, politics, education, (formal and informal), economy, law and health as social institutions.⁴

Politics

Politics can be understood as the art of acquiring power for the purpose of mobilizing and sharing resources, managing and enforcing the affairs of public policy and decision towards the regulation of social order. According to Hornby, politics has to do with “the activities involved in getting and using power in public life, and being able to influence decisions that affect a country or a society.”⁵ According to Iwe in Nmah politics is the process of adjustment and inter-play of power and interest within the public life and affairs of a society on national and multi-national levels.⁶ However, Dahl in Okafor sees politics as to who gets what, when and how.⁷ The very decision to support a particular religion or set of principles in a society as opposed to an individual is a political decision. Politics summarily deals with governance, mobilization of human and other human resources, enforcing the affairs of public policy, decision making and resource sharing for the purpose of achieving national goals.

Nation building

Egodi refers to a number of things as nation building. Among them is the deliberate effort by which , through articulated programs and policies, the different peoples of Nigeria while retaining their cultural diversity, would become effectively integrated as one or made to regard themselves as having a lot more in common than they ever thought they did... and as well, attain infrastructural development.⁸ Nation building entails the processes and efforts by which the citizens create favourable environment in the state for the purpose of achieving and maximizing good life for its citizens. Ekeia opines that nation building is not a causal process but an all-involving and conscious political, social, religious, economic and ethical process under an effective leadership.⁹ The sole purpose of nation building therefore is to provide good life for citizens as Aristotle opines that the main reason for the existence of the state is for the sake of good life for the citizens. Moreover, nation building incorporates both the leaders and the led. It means that all hands should be on deck to achieve the good life in question.

The Problems of Religion and Politics in Nigeria

The problems associated with religion and politics in Nigeria are diverse and rooted on certain unguarded factors. Among these factors are religions faith conceptualization, differences in religious world-view and beliefs, perception, religious sentiments, compromise of ideal political philosophy and impracticability of secularism in Nigeria. Nigeria has three main religions: African Traditional Religion, Islam and Christianity. However, there are crystal differences in faith conceptualization, philosophy and articulation of these three religions. Christianity and Islam for instance, are independently separate in faith ideology, philosophy and articulation and as well, founders. According to Ougua and Ougua, Christianity is not a parallel concept to Islam; nor is Christianization a parallel concept to Islamization. Each is in a world of its own. In terms of proselytization, Christianity concerns itself with conversion of willing persons; Islam concerns itself with conversion of persons in the spheres of religion and politics with the use of force”.¹⁰Undoubtedly, the above differences have contributed enormously to religio-political conflicts and agitations including demands for faith- based representation in governance and inclusiveness in political appointments, especially, at the federal levels between Muslims and Christians.

Furthermore, there are problems associated with religious intolerance cum inseparability of religion from human private and public affairs or political activities in Nigeria since humans, as religious beings from time immemorial are saddled with the responsibility of having their actions and activities determined and conditioned by the Supreme Being. While, scholars, however, are varied in opinion on whether Supreme Being should determine human activities and actions as divine command or not, religion, nevertheless, holds by all intent an indisputable sway in human existence, activities and actions. Hence; it is believed that all power belongs to God. In a way to resolve the complex problems and conflicts associated with human action and activities, especially, religion and politics, Udoiem opines, that “some have called for the separation of religion and politics in human public affairs while others maintain that all political actions and human affairs should be directed by religion. He further expresses the fact that, the situation becomes even more complex where those who hold that religion and politics should be inseparable in the determination of human actions both in private and public life, and those who hold that there should be a separation of religion and politics in human affairs co-exist in the same community.”¹¹

Therefore, separating religion from private and public affairs as a way of solving the problems associated with religion and political musketeers in Nigeria remains an illusionary chase despite the concept and adoption of secularism. According to Egodi, in the past four decades of our Nigerian Independence, ethnic consciousness, political polarization and religious differences have intermittently affected mutual relationship and inter group interaction in the country in a negative way. Hence; before the end of the nation’s civil war, ethnicity was the bane of Nigeria’s political unity and social harmony. Unfortunately, this has been succeeded in the subtlest manner, especially, since 1997/98, by an inter-play of a combination of political and religious factors with religion becoming more of a divisive factor. Today, attempts to hold political leaders accountable in Nigeria, conduct free and fair elections, maintain social mutual coexistence and to constructively criticize the actions and policies of our leaders, meet serious opposition, resistance and blackmail on the ground of religion, political party or tribal sentiments. These problematic factors remain clogs in the wheel of our nation building; sustainability and development, since the majority of citizens respond to politics, electioneering and governance on the basis of tribe and religious persuasion of the candidates.

Influence of Religion on Nigerian Politics

At this juncture, we shall proceed to establish how religion has influenced the Nigerian political space in a negative manner. This will form the thrust of this debate that misuse of religion affects leadership and other public affairs by creating a political system that makes the pursuit and realization of nation building near impossible. A cursory study below is pointing at certain underlining factors but not limited as triggers of such influence.

(1)Doctrinal cum Perception factors: Ataullah Siddiqui in his book, *Christian – Muslim Dialogue in the Twentieth Century* states that religions do not meet in vacuum; rather it is their followers who encounter each

other. He notes that the perception and apprehensions of members of varied religious groups are molded by events, which play an important role in their understanding of each other.¹² Events such as religious doctrine and philosophy are strong molders of belief system, perception and disposition (character) in understanding and relating with one another both in public and community life. For instance, the postulation that Islamic philosophers divided the world into two camps- believers and infidels, for such division and ideology may have had its origin from the Holy Quran 9:5 which reads: then kill the polytheists (which is synonymous with unbelievers / infidel by translation from the word *Kafir*) wherever you find them and capture them and besiege them and sit in wait for them at every place of ambush.

While Muslim adherents are referred to as believers and have been given the final revelation in the *Qur'an*, *infidels* are non-believers with the possible effects of humiliation, and ultimately death or conversion. To Islamic purists, all other religions are either heretical or corrupt. Hence, Udoidem notes that, Muslims believe that there is only one God and Muhammed His only true prophet. Christianity in the other hand regards non adherents to their faith as unbelievers and pagans whose eternal destiny is hell fire and as well, believes and holds Christ as the last revelation and Saviour of the world.

According to Egodi, Islam did not appear as conservative as modern realities in Nigeria presents and as many Muslim apologetics presume. Purists divided the world into two: *dar al-Islam* (territory under Muslim rule) and *dar al-harb* (territory under non – Muslim rule), and determine the status of persons by their religious affiliation. While religious liberalists and apologists advocate for peaceful co-existence, cooperate and mutual politics and social harmony irrespective of religious leaning, division of the world into separate camps by doctrine and philosophical postulation has some probabilities of negative influence on perception and disposition of adherents, especially, the fundamentalists and the unlettered. This has resulted to hatred, growing violence and armed conflicts across the globe with its attendant effects on political and economic life of nations.

(2)Politics of Religious Sentiments: Politics in Nigeria has been keenly and heavily polarized through religious sentiments. In many instances, campaigns and voting are characterized and predicated on religious and ethnic sentiments, especially, at the national levels rather than character, capacity and competence. This is done either to canvass support for the candidate of a particular religion or to discourage or dissuade the electorates from voting a particular candidate outside their religious preference. Moreover, to control political powers and influence policies in favour and in advancement of a particular religious faith, using political power. It is glaring that religion was greatly deployed in the last 2023 presidential cum national assembly elections as strategy to outwit the other. Sequel to this, the Punch Newspaper by Leke captured the former speaker, Femi Gbajabamila assertion that the just concluded presidential and national assembly elections were about ethnicity and religion rather than performance and competence of the candidates.¹³ To this effect, Williams maintains that “when societies become more heterogeneous, due to culture contact and sharper lines of stratification, some members of society acquire an instrumental attitude towards religion. That is, the ruling class begins to see it as a means of preserving order that is helping to guarantee their position”¹⁴

(3)Compromise of Nigerian secularity: Nigeria is a secular state in principle and not in practice as a result of the lack of clear divorce of undue religious influence in our politics or lack of political will to curtail undue religious influences in our politics. By secularity, Kambassay cited in Williams opines that it is a belief in secularism and state of being neutral in religious affairs, neither opposing nor promoting religion. Far from being totally uninterested in religion, it acknowledges the existence of religion, appreciates the fact that members of its secular community are at the same time adherents to diverse religious beliefs. As such, it respects those beliefs while at the same time keeps an eye on religion, so that religion does not overstep its boundaries to infringe in matters of public interest thereby jeopardizing public peace. Instances of non-adherence or compromise of constitutional secularism include government establishment of Welfare Pilgrim Boards for both Christians and Muslims in Nigeria, with the whopping resources disbursed annually on pilgrimage to Mecca and Jerusalem for no specified socio-economic benefits to the general public. The sponsorship has made the event an appendage of political activity and influence in Nigeria. Moreover, the dual existential judicial systems in Nigeria via

introduction of Sharia courts in the 1979 constitution for certain adjudication in a pre-supposed secular state, the use of religious gatherings and places of worship for political campaigns, building of central Mosque and Christian Center in Aso Rock at Abuja supported by government and probably being maintained with public funds, among other interferences. Today, some government officials feature religious rituals in public offices, institutions and functionaries. Churches, Mosques, Chapels, Priests and Imams compete with one another in government houses, institutions and functions just to gain upper influence and control.

(4) Unguarded utterances (polemics) of some religious leaders on political matters. Religious leaders are known as opinion leaders in any society. On the contrary, unguarded and unconstructive utterances, polemical writings or statements by religious leaders can create confusion and deceive even the gullible in taking correct political decisions and at times, opposing reactions that causes violence. Madu gives instance of such unguarded media report by the late Sheikh or Gumi's statement "that Muslims would not accept a Christian president in the third republic."¹⁵ Such utterance undoubtedly was met with stiff opposing reactions. The 2023 presidential and national assembly elections witnessed diverse unguarded statements by some religious and political leaders across religions, especially, the fall out of APC presidential primaries that produced Muslim- Muslim ticket. Some of these ambivalent roles are played at the pulpits and on social media outlets. The effect usually is diversionary of the gullible on core political matters and do generate violence as such statements attract opposing reactions from the other religious groups.

Religious Values and Nation Building

Political stability, peace, unity, competence, economic and human development are components and ingredients of nation building. Religion, on the other hand, plays multi-facial synergy roles in achieving the above virtues in human society. Among these roles are:

- (1) **Peace building:** Peace is a necessary condition for nation building. Interestingly, the three major religions in Nigeria namely: Christianity, Islam and Indigenous religions all advocate and propagate peace. Indigenous religion celebrates an annual week of peace, as acknowledged by Achebe in his book "*Things Fall Apart*". He explained how Okonkwo desecrated the week of peace by breaking the rule of that week in the society and was punished.¹⁶ Accordingly, no work is done during the week of peace; people call on their neighbours and drink wine. The people are not supposed to utter harsh words. Hence; it is time for mutual interaction, merriment and entertainment. The illustration of week of peace by Achebe is a practical demonstration of the inherent peace and peace value in Indigenous religion. Christians and Muslims alike have had occasions of advocating for peace, praying for peace and preaching peace to members and non- members. Peace in general, is cardinal in the teachings of all religions. It is therefore, relatively impossible to experience healthy politics, attract investments and development without peaceful environment.
- (2) **Human and Leadership Ethical development:** Ethics as laws of morality and formulation of rules of conduct is critical in leadership and human character development. The major discontent in today's Nigeria leadership experience is probably the lack or subversion of ethical culture in politics and governance. The astonishing consequences of this abound with moral vices eating up in alarming proportions our system, be it social, legal, political, educational, and economic and as well, other institutions of our society. Religion as human oriented discipline is primed with ethical values of character, justice, accountability, integrity, fairness, trustfulness, compliance to rule of law and these are indispensable in ethical leadership and human character development. Religion by implication contributes in building human beings that build the nation.
- (3) **Advocacy for human rights and dignity:** Nmah asserts that the object of the church in politics is to restore human dignity, rights and human values.¹⁵ Fundamental to nation building is protection of human rights as granted by the Nigerian constitution and other international conventions. Human rights by naturalists are first conferred by God and this predates other school of thoughts on human rights such as the positivists and socialists. The magnitude of violation of human rights and dignity of persons in our society today in all spheres of life should be a serious concern to faith based organizations in Nigeria. Hence; Appadorai

maintains that “the duty of state is to seek and recognize the rights of individuals to live a good life and this can be defined only in moral context.”¹⁸ Consequently, religion should influence politicians to respect and ensure that human rights are granted to all persons irrespective of status or class. For this is the benchmark of true democracy in a civilized society devoid of election rigging, manipulation and imposition of leaders on the good citizens of the country.

(4) Human Spiritual Development

Another key function of religion is building of spiritual life of people. Since, human beings are religious beings with hunger for spiritual satisfaction. Spiritual satisfaction comes with inner awareness of God, cooperate and individual fellowship with God in word and prayers among other religious rituals necessary for spiritual enlightenments. Besides, all religions hold the view of afterlife. Religions exist to proffer answers to human quest for the unknown and life beyond as enshrined in the holy book whether in Islam or Christianity.

Implications of Negative Influence of Religion on Nigerian Politics

The influence of religion in Nigerian politics has diverse implications for nation building. Among the implications are its contribution to leadership failure in Nigeria due to the distortive effects of religious sentiments on politics, its processes and bureaucracy. As a result, the system keep having leaders with scrimpy or lack of moral capacity, integrity, competence and accountability, sound economic policies, political and intellectual sagacity needed to drive the nation towards development. As such, Nigeria has continued to have corrupt and incompetent politicians who made their way to political power at different levels of government through the aid of religious sentiments. Moreover, it affects the nation’s bureaucracy in terms of appointment of managers and directors of agencies and heads of institutions. Besides, our democratic values of free and fair elections, equity and justice among other crucial values have been variously distorted and eroded.

In addition are the constant religious and political induced conflicts. Nigeria with her multi-ethnic, cultural and religious diversities is yet to break out from the jinxes of ethnic and religious inclinations. Hence; conflicts associated with religion and politics heavily affects nation building, its components and processes, directly and indirectly. Influence of religion in politics has the probabilities of undermining both the mandate of the church and other religious bodies of inculcating the values indispensable for ethical leadership in Nigeria. From history, religion has had a touch and role in political and leadership evolution of nations, through advocating for quality and patriotic leadership, rights of citizens and freedom of the oppressed via good governance, functional justice system and morality across the world including Africa. Besides stabilizing the psychological and emotional challenges, that may arise with the changes in political leadership or introduction and execution of new social programmes needed for development. Other implications are the use of religion as a safe haven for corrupt politicians who allegedly misappropriated government funds on the ground of religion or ethnic leaning. Finally, religious influence in politics undermines the potency of Nigerian secularism. Since, there exist religious consideration and patronage in political appointments and electioneering rather than capacity and competence.

Conclusion

Religion from time immemorial has demonstrated potent force and influence in human society. As such, it has variously contributed in building human moral and spiritual lives as well as social institutions such as education, economy, medicine, politics to mention just a few. Unfortunately, the deployment of religion by some political elites into the political space via religious sentiments just to gain political advantage and position has caused lots of distortions to our political processes and nation building. The work sees this development as an aberration and a deviation from the true essence of leadership, religion and politics of social contract. Some causative factors responsible for this trend and unhealthy development were examined and as well, religious values capable of inculcating and reinvigorating ethical leadership and sense of patriotism in leadership. The implications for nation

building are plethora. Hence; the national bureaucracy, nation building components, political leadership among others are all causalities of this organized infiltration as being reflected today in our nation.

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